

1 Is the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) index an adequate 2 framework to measure the progress of the 2030 Agenda?

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12 **Abstract**

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14 Under the consideration of different measures adopted by most United Nations (UN) states
15 members, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) included in the 2030 Agenda for
16 Sustainable Development aim to address main challenges related to social, economic and
17 environmental issues. Numerous single indicators have been established to monitor progress
18 towards sustainable development; however, the need for benchmarking the degree of
19 sustainability of countries triggered the creation of the SDG Index, which originally compiled
20 77 indicators and has evolved to 99 at present. This research analyses the suitability of applying
21 this composite index for assessing the fulfilment of the 2030 Agenda. The scarce availability
22 of information resulted in 60% of the SDGs indicators being disregarded in the SDG Index.
23 The scores obtained through the application of this index clustered UN countries according to
24 specific geographic areas, highlighting the need for developing regional SDG Indices to
25 emphasize the achievement of lower-performed goals.
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28 **Keywords**

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30 2030 Agenda; Sustainability indicators; Sustainable Development Goals; SDG Index;
31 Sustainable development.
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33 **1. Introduction**

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35 Sustainable development is an unclear concept which can lead to misunderstandings due to
36 its multiple and varied definitions (Hopwood et al., 2005). However, there is general consensus
37 about its complexity, uncertainty and multidimensional character, which requires an in-depth
38 analysis of different magnitudes (time, space, function), multiple players (economic, social)
39 and diverse systemic interrelations (Kemp and Martens, 2007).

40 With the publication of “the Brundtland Report” in 1987 by the World Commission on
41 Environment and Development (WCED), the term sustainable development was coined as an
42 attempt to link environment with development, being defined as “the development that meets
43 needs of current generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their
44 own needs” (WCED, 1987). In order to operationalize this new concept, three pillars arose to
45 undertake joint approaches of sustainable development issues, namely society, environment and
46 economy. The bias towards some of these pillars in detriment of a global perspective difficulties
47 the assessment of their overlaps and interdependencies, promoting the continued separation of
48 social, economic and environmental analyses (Kemp et al., 2005).

49 Sustainability indicators emerged to satisfy the requirement of measuring the progress of
50 sustainable development and facilitate decision-making processes under the consideration of its
51 three dimensions. The Commission on Sustainable Development (CSD) was in charge of
52 developing and implementing national indicators of sustainable development (UN, 2007),
53 whose last revised edition was launched in 2007 to support mainly developing countries. Most
54 world leaders approved the UN Millennium Declaration in September 2000 (UN, 2000),
55 including 8 Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) to face major issues under a global
56 partnership commitment by 2015. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development was adopted
57 at the UN Sustainable Development Summit (UN-Habitat, 2015a) in September 2015,
58 considering a set of 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) which replaced the MDGs and
59 must be reached before the end of 2030.

60 This research aimed at evaluating the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) Index to
61 ascertain its suitability as an accurate and representative country-scale metric of all the
62 indicators contemplated in the 17 SDGs of the 2030 Agenda. An assessment was also conducted
63 to determine whether the elements contained in several sustainability aggregate indices,
64 international initiatives such as the Agenda 21, the implementation plan of the World Summit
65 on Sustainable Development held in Johannesburg and the 2007 CSD indicators were equally
66 weighted with respect to the three sustainability pillars. The article concluded by discussing
67 data collected in 2017 related to the SDG index of 157 countries worldwide.

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69 **2. Global Sustainability Indices**

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71 The multidisciplinary nature of sustainable development and the difficulties to recognize its
72 meaning (Basiago, 1995) greatly complicates its monitoring using single indicators. Hence,
73 integrated frameworks are necessary to consider interdependence of social, economic and
74 environmental aspects holistically (Devuyst, 2000). Sustainability indices for countries provide
75 unidimensional values that aggregate national information on the three sustainability
76 dimensions essential to compare the performance among different countries in the long term.
77 Still, these metrics cannot properly reflect the individual effect of multi-country interactions on
78 each nation in terms of sustainable development.

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80 **2.1. Human Development Indices**

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82 The Human Development Index (HDI) was launched in 1990 by the Human Development
83 Reports Office of the UN Development Programme (UNDP, 2016) to reflect three aspects, such
84 as a long and healthy life, access to knowledge and decent standard of living, emphasizing that
85 economic growth is not the only factor to appraise the development of countries. The HDI is
86 calculated as the geometric mean of three normalized sub-indices representing Life Expectancy
87 Index, Education Index and Gross National Index (GNI). The HDI groups all countries into
88 four human development categories: very high (> 0.8), high ($0.7 - 0.799$), medium ($0.55 -$
89 0.699) and low (< 0.55).

90 After some adjustments made on the HDI, a series of additional related indices emerged
91 (UNDP, 2016). The Inequality-adjusted Human Development Index (IHDI) incorporates
92 inequality element into each HDI sub-index. The Gender Development Index (GDI) includes
93 gender disparities, calculated as the ratio of female HDI to male HDI. The Gender Inequality
94 Index (GII) gathers the loss of potential human development due to gender inequalities in
95 health, empowerment and labor market. Finally, the Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI)
96 reflects shortages at household level in health, education and standard of living.

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98 **2.2. Environmental Sustainability Development Indices**

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100 In 1990, the University of British Columbia presented the Ecological Footprint (EF)
101 (Wackernagel, 1994) to determine the Earth's surface required to cover the consumption of
102 natural resources by a defined population. Cropland, grazing land, fishing grounds, built land,
103 forest area and carbon demand on land are the six categories of productive surface areas
104 involved in this metric. The Worldwide Wildlife Foundation (WWF) and the Zoological
105 Society of London (ZSL) conceived the Living Planet Index (LPI) in 1970 (WWF, 2016), which
106 appraises the state of biological diversity based on the analysis of more than 18,000 vertebrate
107 populations around the world over time.

108 Yale University, Columbia University and the World Economic Forum jointly launched the
109 Environmental Sustainability Index (ESI) in 2000 (Esty et al., 2005), a composite metric to
110 assess the progress towards environmental sustainability by comparing the performance of 146
111 countries across five topics: environmental systems, reducing environmental stresses, reducing
112 vulnerability to environmental stresses, societal and institutional capacity to respond to
113 environmental challenges and global stewardship. The score is based on the arithmetic mean of
114 21 indicators comprising 76 different variables.

115 After the 2005 ESI report, this index evolved to the Environmental Performance Index (EPI)
116 (Hsu et al., 2016). The current 2016 EPI is a comparative framework which ranks the

117 environmental performance of 180 nations based on the protection of human health and
118 ecosystems, representing some targets included in SDGs and encompassing more than 20
119 indicators grouped into 9 categories: health impacts, air quality, water and sanitation, water
120 resources, agriculture, forests, fisheries, biodiversity and habitat and climate and energy.

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122 **2.3. Well-being Assessment Method**

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124 The Wellbeing Assessment is the result of the two-stage collaboration between the
125 International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) and the International Development
126 Research Centre (IDRC). The first phase, from 1994 to 1996, served to create the Barometer of
127 Sustainability (IUCN, 1996), whilst the second step, from 1997 to 1999, allowed to devise the
128 Well-being Assessment Method (Prescott-Allen, 2001), initially applied to 180 countries as the
129 first global assessment of sustainability that combined four indices: Human Wellbeing Index
130 (HWI), Ecosystem Wellbeing Index (EWI), Wellbeing Index (WI) and Wellbeing/Stress Index
131 (WSI).

132 HWI appraises quality of life through the average of 36 indicators related to health and
133 population, wealth, knowledge and culture, community and equity. Environment is measured
134 by EWI as the average of 51 indicators involving land, air, species and genes, water and
135 resource use aspects. WI juxtaposes HWI and EWI to evaluate the combination between human
136 and ecosystem wellbeing in societies to achieve sustainability. WSI reflects the impact of
137 society development on the environment as the ratio of human wellbeing to ecosystem stress.

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139 **2.4. Urban Sustainability Indices**

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141 Before the Second UN Conference on Human Settlements (Habitat II) in 1996, the UN
142 Centre for Human Settlements (UN-Habitat) developed a pioneer composite index known as
143 City Development Index (CDI) (UN, 2017) to grade cities according to their urban development
144 based on livability, poverty, traffic congestion, inclusiveness and sustainability factors.

145 The City Prosperity Index and the Wheel of Urban Prosperity were launched in 2012 by
146 UN-Habitat to assess urban sustainability (UN-Habitat, 2012). One year later, the City
147 Prosperity Index was transformed into a new global initiative known as City Prosperity
148 Initiative (CPI) (UN-Habitat, 2015b), based on spatial analyses that can support local, regional
149 and national decision-makers. There are four scenarios measured by CPI: the Global City
150 Ranking, a global and regional monitoring framework; the Basic CPI, an initial diagnosis
151 internationally comparable; the extended CPI, an in-depth analysis comparable within the
152 country; and the Contextual CPI, an urban monitoring tool including national urban policies
153 (UN-Habitat, 2016).

154 The outstanding role played by buildings in the most developed countries due inter alia to
155 energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions triggered the appearance of rating systems
156 to assess the sustainability of these elements more than two decades ago (Berardi, 2013a). The
157 scope of these frameworks was soon extended to cover communities and cities, as a
158 consequence of the effects on sustainability derived from the rising concentration of population
159 in urban areas (Berardi, 2013b). Thus, some tools such as BREEAM for Communities, LEED
160 for Neighbourhood Development and CASBEE for Urban Development were introduced in the
161 sustainability assessment of communities and cities.

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163 **2.5. Economic Sustainability Indices**

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165 Nordhaus and Tobin (1972) introduced a metric called Measure of Economic Welfare
166 (MEW), which adjusted the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) by adding values of leisure time,
167 unpaid work and subtracting environmental damage value due to industrial production and
168 consumption. From MEW, Daly and Cobb (1989) devised the Index of Sustainable Economic
169 Welfare (ISEW) in 1989, which incorporated natural resource depletion and environmental
170 damage costs into the assessment. Leisure time was omitted from ISEW and the valuation of
171 household work differed from that in MEW.

172 The Genuine Progress Indicator (GPI), conceived in 1995, is a later variant of ISEW.
173 Although both of them use the same income framework than GDP, they also contemplate other
174 deductions related to inequality, crime costs, environmental damages and reduction of leisure
175 time. Furthermore, consumer durables, public infrastructure, volunteering and household works
176 are also deemed in these metrics (Talberth et al., 2006).

177 The Adjusted Net Saving Index (ANSI), also known as Genuine Savings Index (GSI),
178 measures the net annual national wealth variation considering human, nature and economic
179 dimensions (Hamilton and Clemens, 1999). Positive values reflect that generations will receive
180 wealth in the future, otherwise sustainability is not guaranteed.

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182 **2.6. Other International Sustainable Development Endeavours**

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184 The statistical office of the European Union (Eurostat) produced diverse sustainable
185 development indicators (SDIs) from 1997 to 2001. The first EU SDI was approved by the
186 European Commission in 2005, providing the basis for current SDIs. This framework,
187 encompassing 130 indicators, covers the economic, social, environmental and institutional
188 dimensions by assessing ten different aspects, such as socioeconomic development, sustainable
189 consumption and production, social inclusion, demographic changes, public health, climate
190 change and energy, sustainable transport, natural resources, global partnership and good
191 governance.

192 Before implementing the SDGs, all 34 OECD countries were evaluated from the perspective
193 of this new framework through the first world SDG Index at a country level, as described in the
194 2015 SDG Index Report (Kroll, 2015), by calculating the unweighted arithmetic mean of 34
195 indicator scores on a scale 1-10 on behalf of the 17 SDGs.

196 The Mediterranean Strategy for Sustainable Development (MSSD) was adopted in the
197 Barcelona Convention COP19 as a strategic policy framework to align sustainable development
198 in the Mediterranean region with the SDGs in the period from 2016 to 2025. This strategy aims
199 at achieving six objectives involving marine and coastal areas, rural development,
200 Mediterranean cities, climate change, promoted green and blue economy and enhanced
201 governance (UNEP/MAP, 2016).

202 The Baltic 2030 Action Plan (CBSS, 2017) was approved by the Ministers of Foreign
203 Affairs of the Baltic Sea Region on June 2017 to reach the goals of the 2030 Agenda in this
204 geographical zone. The plan mainly focused on six areas correlated with the SDGs, such as
205 partnership for sustainable development, transition to a sustainable economy, climate change
206 action, equality and social wellbeing, resilient cities and communities and enhanced education.

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208 **2.7. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) Index**

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210 The generic definition of sustainable development presented in the Brundtland Report was
211 elaborated in much greater detail in the 2030 Agenda through the implementation of the SDGs,
212 which aim at ending poverty and hunger while addressing environmental concerns without
213 overlooking social challenges related to wellbeing, health and education (Cörvers et al., 2016).

214 The 17 SDGs comprise 169 targets and 232 indicators to monitor progress towards the
215 achievement of social, economic and environmental goals before the end of 2030. All indicators
216 were grouped into three tiers according to data availability and the statistical methodology
217 followed. Tier I compiles 98 indicators whose statistical methodologies were based on regularly
218 available data, whilst Tier II gathers 50 indicators with scarce access to information but clear
219 statistical frameworks. Finally, the 79 indicators belonging to Tier III lack both data and
220 statistical standards. Furthermore, 15 indicators are pending of assignment to a specific tier.

221 Bertelsmann Stiftung (BS) and the Sustainable Development Solutions Network (SDSN)
222 devised the SDG Index in 2015 as a composite system to benchmark the performance of
223 countries across the SDGs. Regarding data availability, some indicators were selected to
224 represent each SDG on a scale in the range 0-100. Hence, the SDG Index of a country is the
225 arithmetic mean of all its SDGs scores (Sachs et al., 2016). Whilst the first report of the index
226 launched in 2016 involved 77 indicators covering 149 countries, the 2017 edition was extended
227 to include 99 indicators and 157 UN member nations (Sachs et al., 2017).

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229 **3. Assessment and discussion of the 2017 SDG Index**

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Three rounds of questionnaires based on the Delphi method were addressed to experts from Academy to classify all the elements of global initiatives and the SDG Index and SDGs indicators across the sustainability dimensions according to their convergence. Then, the 2017 SDG Index indicators were grouped into the SDGs categories to determine whether their distribution was consistent with that of the 2030 Agenda. Finally, this section examines the scores reached by all countries and geographical areas in the 2017 SDG Index, determining the regions whose SDG marks were above and below average scores.

3.1. Weighting of sustainability dimensions in the sustainable development endeavours.

In Figure 1, all the sections covered by the Agenda 21, chapters of Johannesburg Summit Implementation Plan, 2007 CSD indicators and the 17 SDGs were grouped into environmental, social, economic and governance categories according to the Delphi methodology. The chart reflects the evolution in the attention paid to each sustainable dimension across different international actions undertaken during the last decades.

The preponderance of environmental matters turned from 34% in the pioneer Agenda 21 to 18% in the SDGs. Overall, the former emphasized the relevance of environmental and governance aspects, which involved a third part of the total amount of their elements, whilst the latter highlights the predominance of social aspects (47%). Consequently, the importance of environmental concerns has diminished in detriment of social and economic factors.

Figure 1. Distribution of global initiative elements in each sustainability dimension (UNCED, 1992; UN, 2002; UN, 2007; UN-Habitat, 2015a)

3.2. Correlation between the 2017 SDG Index and the SDGs indicators

Since the 2017 SDG Index is intended to reflect the performance of the SDGs indicators at a country scale, Table 1 shows the distribution of the latter in the composite index, in order to determine whether their relative weights per SDG were altered significantly. Thus, the relevance allocated by the 2030 Agenda to each SDG could also be substantially modified,

263 distorting the principles derived from the resolution adopted at the UN Sustainable
264 Development Summit. The results revealed a gap between both frameworks. SDGs #1, 10, 11
265 and 17 showed a reduction between 29% and 54% in the amount of 2017 SDG Index indicators
266 in relation to the SDGs. This decrease was more moderate for SDGs #5, 6 and 8, not exceeding
267 16.5%. SDGs #11 and 17 experienced the highest fall with 49.75% and 53.20% each. SDGs #3,
268 7, 9, 12 and 13 presented an increase in the indicators of the 2017 SDG Index from 35% to
269 76%, whilst the growth in SDGs #4 and 14 fluctuated between 6% and 18%. SDG #2, 15 and
270 16 remained in similar figures. Finally, the SDG #9 exhibited the major rise in the amount of
271 indicators considered (75.82%).

272 **Table 1.** Comparison of indicators considered by the SDGs and 2017 SDG Index (Sachs et al., 2017)

SDG	Concept	SDG Indicators	% SDG Indicators	2017 SDG Index Indicators	% 2017 SDG Index Indicators	Difference (%)
1	No poverty	11	4.74	3	3.03	-36.08
2	Zero hunger	14	6.03	6	6.06	0.50
3	Good health and wellbeing	26	11.21	15	15.16	35.24
4	Quality education	11	4.74	5	5.05	6.54
5	Gender equality	14	6.03	5	5.05	-16.25
6	Clean water and sanitation	11	4.74	4	4.04	-14.77
7	Affordable and clean energy	6	2.59	4	4.04	55.98
8	Decent work and economic growth	16	6.90	6	6.06	-12.17
9	Industry, innovation and infrastructure	12	5.17	9	9.09	75.82
10	Reduced inequalities	10	4.31	3	3.03	-29.70
11	Sustainable cities and communities	14	6.03	3	3.03	-49.75
12	Responsible consumption and production	12	5.17	8	8.08	56.28
13	Climate action	6	2.59	4	4.04	55.98
14	Life below water	10	4.31	5	5.05	17.17
15	Life on land	12	5.17	5	5.05	-2.32
16	Peace, justice and strong institutions	22	9.48	9	9.09	-4.11
17	Partnerships for the goals	25	10.79	5	5.05	-53.20
Total		232	100.00	99	100.00	

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274 **Figure 2** illustrates the allocation of indicators across the sustainability dimensions.
 275 Although the relative predominance of categories was maintained in the SDGs and 2017 SDG
 276 Index indicators, all percentages changed. The social and governance dimensions were
 277 reduced by 2% and 50%, approximately. In contrast, the economic and environmental pillars
 278 rose 6% and 2%, respectively. Regarding the indicators of the 2017 SDG Index, the social
 279 dimension emerged as the most relevant one (51%), followed by the economic aspect (30%).
 280 Only 14% and 5% of the indicators were related to requirements of environment and
 281 governance, respectively.

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Figure 2. Allocation of the SDGs and 2017 SDG Index indicators across the sustainability pillars (UN-Habitat, 2015a; Sachs et al., 2017)

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3.3. 2017 SDG Index scores

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Table 2 contains the SDGs average scores reached by major geographical regions according to the 2017 SDG Index Report, which includes datasets from 157 out of 193 UN states members. Having a population density over one million of inhabitants and available data for at least 80% of the SDG Index indicators were the two mandatory requirements to incorporate a country into the study. However, some states with less than one million people were also considered due to information availability.

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Overall, higher SDGs marks corresponded to Europe, North America and Oceania, except for SDGs #12 and 13, which were better performed by Asia, Africa and Latin America & Caribbean (LAC). Whilst North America reached the lowest rates in SDGs #12 and 17, the poorest marks in SDGs #13 and 15 were for Oceania, being LAC the least valued region in SDG #16. Africa received the lowest scores in the rest of SDGs. The low scores achieved by high-income countries was due to the inclusion of nine spillover indicators, which aim at assessing the positive and/or negative impacts of a country on other states to reach their goals. Spillovers are grouped into three categories: environment, governance and economy. Among them, pollutants, groundwater depletion and biodiversity loss because of trade, international development aid, financial secrecy, tax havens and arms dealing are aspects that must be highlighted. Whilst great imported carbon emissions penalized Australia, groundwater depletion and biodiversity impacts had a negative effect on Canada and New Zealand. U.S. achieved high marks in finance and security areas.

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SDG #1 could be considered eradicated worldwide except in Africa, which showed scores below 90 except for some countries in the North. SDG #14 performed very poorly in general, with ratings from 42 to 56 for all regions, reflecting the negative impacts of spillovers on

311 pollutants and the use of global commons such as high seas and oceans. Moreover, SDG #14
 312 was affected by data gaps. For instance, some of its indicators were neither among desired
 313 metrics nor included in the UN Statistics Commission list, being obtained from less reliable
 314 sources, such as the Ocean Health Index and Birdlife International. SDGs #4, 6 and 11 reached
 315 marks over 90 in Europe, North America and Oceania, but only the two latter scored over 90
 316 with respect to SDG #3. These scores are intimately linked with the high level of development
 317 in these zones. Africa, Asia and LAC achieved the lowest scores in relation to SDG #9 (from
 318 14 to 33), as a consequence of the scarce international development support. Finally, SDGs
 319 #2, 5, 6 and 11 reached the poorest marks in Africa and Asia.

320 **Figure 3** shows the distribution of countries across regions in three ranking groups
 321 covering 2016 and 2017 SDG Index reports. Although scores of both composite indicators are
 322 not directly comparable due to minor changes incorporated into the calculation methodology
 323 of the 2017 SDG Index, the chart illustrates a clear trend in the ranking according to the
 324 geographical distribution. Most nations in Europe, North America and Oceania occupied the
 325 Top 50, whilst Asia and LAC put the majority of their countries in the second group (from 51
 326 to 100) and the bulk of African nations were placed in the last group. No significant changes
 327 were identified in 2016 and 2017 for higher economies, except for the Russian Federation and
 328 Turkey moving from the Top 50 to the next range because of the spillover indicators: arms
 329 export and financial secrecy, respectively. Africa also experienced a deterioration, with 4
 330 countries (Cabo Verde, Mauritius, South Africa and Botswana) leaving group II to be
 331 integrated in the last category. Whilst Cabo Verde vanished from the 2017 SDG Index and
 332 South Africa lost several positions due to its poor score in SDG #10, Mauritius and Botswana
 333 ranked the highest across pollutants spillovers. The incorporation of three new Asian nations
 334 (Turkmenistan, Syrian Arab Republic and Timor) increased the countries in the third group.
 335 Furthermore, Saudi Arabia and Kuwait descended to this category due to ground water
 336 depletion, pollutants and biodiversity loss spillovers.

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Table 2. Average score per region across the 2017 SDG Index indicators (Sachs et al., 2017)

SDG#	Worldwide (157)	Europe (41)	North America (2)	Oceania (2)	Asia (42)	LAC (26)	Africa (44)
SDG1	85.2	99.5	99.5	99.9	94.7	91.7	58.1
SDG2	52.4	63.2	67.0	61.8	50.9	52.9	42.4
SDG3	70.7	87.7	92.5	94.3	72.7	77.3	47.1
SDG4	72.3	90.2	96.0	95.7	75.5	76.3	48.2
SDG5	59.9	70.3	77.0	79.5	53.4	67.8	50.0
SDG6	78.3	92.9	92.1	96.0	72.7	86.9	63.6
SDG7	66.1	85.3	89.3	88.4	70.7	78.8	34.2
SDG8	61.9	76.4	84.6	80.1	64.3	63.1	43.6

SDG9	33.5	55.4	79.8	77.2	32.4	26.1	14.3
SDG10	62.5	82.9	66.2	73.1	70.6	36.9	48.9
SDG11	73.6	91.8	98.9	100	64.1	85.6	56.3
SDG12	68.9	59.2	45.5	52.8	70.5	70.7	77.3
SDG13	78.8	80.4	60.1	57.0	77.3	81.3	79.0
SDG 14	45.5	51.8	50.4	55.9	42.3	44.5	42.0
SDG15	59.9	69.4	47.9	41.8	49.2	56.1	64.7
SDG16	63.3	71.3	74.8	83.9	66.7	52.0	57.9
SDG17	65.0	64.5	57.4	65.3	60.9	70.5	66.5
SDG Index	64.8	76.4	75.2	76.7	64.3	66.1	52.8

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Figure 3. Distribution of regional areas according to the 2016 and 2017 SDG Index (Sachs et al., 2016; Sachs et al., 2017)

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In order to illustrate the performance of the SDGs in the six regions considered by the report, these were divided into two categories depending on whether they achieved a score below or above the average, as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** Whilst 5 SDGs scores reflected a balance between geographical areas, 11 of them revealed more regions performing above the average, with only one below the mean in most zones. The economic growth was crucial for all these regions above the mean, without any relevant spillover influence. In contrast, Africa was always placed below the average, along with Asia and LAC, which achieved low marks across two SDGs. The SDG #15 score was below the mean in Asia, North America, Oceania and LAC, due to the impact of the biodiversity loss spillover. Among balanced SDGs, there was no evident correlation between high-income regions and scores over the average. The prevalence of Europe, North America and Oceania only corresponded

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355 to SDGs #9 and 14. Whilst the former is clearly associated with wealth, the latter revealed all
 356 marks were very close to the mean, regardless of national income levels. Africa, Asia and
 357 LAC commanded scores in relation SDG #12, because of impacts of pollutants spillovers on
 358 North America, Europe and Oceania. Concerning SDG #13, marks in Asia, North America
 359 and Oceania were below the average as consequence of carbon spillover. Finally, SDG #17
 360 reflected negative effects of tax havens and scarce international development aid spillovers on
 361 Asia, North America and Europe.
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 364 **Figure 4.** SDGs performance in major regions with respect to average scores (Sachs et al., 2017)
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366 **Figure 5** captures the performance of the six regional areas and the compilation of all 157
 367 countries according to the amount of SDGs above average scores. There is no significant
 368 disparity between zones. Whilst Asia, Oceania and LAC comprised 10 SDGs above the mean,
 369 Europe, North America and the set of 157 countries only had 9. Africa was the only region
 370 where more SDGs (9) were below the average.

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 374 **Figure 5.** Regional areas performance with respect to the average SDG score (Sachs et al., 2017)
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376 **Table 3** presents the evolution of the SDG Index ranking for all 34 countries in the
377 Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) from 2016 to 2017.
378 Sweden, Denmark, Finland and Norway are placed in the top 4, but other highly developed
379 economies like Australia, Italy or United States are very far from them. Czech Republic and
380 Poland enhanced their ranking in 2017, showing an increase of 10 and 11 positions,
381 respectively. Other countries like Luxembourg, United States, Turkey and Israel experienced
382 a fall of 17, 17, 19 and 23 places, respectively, as a result of spillover effects. Whilst
383 Luxembourg was impacted by pollutants, biodiversity loss, financial secrecy and tax haven
384 spillovers, Turkey only suffered from financial secrecy effects. Arms dealing, tax haven and
385 financial secrecy spillovers hit the United States, whereas Israel reflected consequences of
386 pollutants, low international development aid, financial secrecy and weapon exports
387 spillovers.

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389 **Table 3.** OECD countries ranking according to the 2016 and 2017 SDG Index (Sachs et al., 2016; Sachs et al., 2017)

OECD Country	2016 SDG Index	2017 SDG Index	Difference SDG Index (2016-17)
Sweden	1	1	0
Denmark	2	2	0
Norway	3	4	-1
Finland	4	3	1
Switzerland	5	8	-3
Germany	6	6	0
Austria	7	7	0
Netherlands	8	13	-5
Iceland	9	14	-5
United Kingdom	10	16	-6
France	11	10	1
Belgium	12	12	0
Canada	13	17	-4
Ireland	14	19	-5
Czech Republic	15	5	10
Luxembourg	16	33	-17
Slovenia	17	9	8
Japan	18	11	7
Australia	20	26	-6
Estonia	21	15	6
New Zealand	22	20	2
Hungary	24	18	6
United States	25	42	-17
Slovak Republic	26	23	3

Korea Republic	27	31	-4
Israel	29	52	-23
Spain	30	25	5
Portugal	34	28	6
Italy	35	30	5
Poland	38	27	11
Greece	39	40	-1
Chile	42	44	-2
Turkey	48	67	-19
Mexico	56	58	-2

390

391 **3.4. Discussion**

392

393 The disturbing effects of climate change announced at the beginning of 90s created a
 394 global sense of alarm which was articulated in some international actions, mostly focused on
 395 environmental issues, such as the Agenda 21. The subsequent progress in understanding the
 396 multidimensional concept called Sustainable Development helped to determine a wide range
 397 of interrelations between environment, society and economy. Furthermore, imprecise
 398 governance procedures facilitated establishing specific measures to enhance the three
 399 sustainability dimensions. Current SDGs are the sample of the evolution in the perception of
 400 sustainability. However, future assessments still need to clarify the linkages among all aspects
 401 of sustainable development.

402 The selection of the SDGs indicators considered in the 2017 SDG Index impacts badly on
 403 the accuracy of the composite indicator, which can omit some key SDGs targets due to data
 404 availability. The UN should review the metrics included in the Agenda 2030 according to
 405 available information at a country scale, in order to preserve the relevance granted to each
 406 sustainability dimension, which was distorted as shown in [Figure 2](#). Population density should
 407 not be a restriction for disqualifying countries from the aggregate index either, since the SDGs
 408 are a global initiative.

409 The inclusion of spillovers is very controversial. Despite they should assess positive and/or
 410 negative impacts of a country on other states to reach their goals, most spillovers contributed
 411 negatively to scores. Moreover, some SDGs primarily oriented to social and economic aspects
 412 (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 10 and 11) were not represented by spillovers. Although this research was
 413 conducted under the consideration of average data, all SDGs aim at reaching very high scores,
 414 even 100%. The performance of the SDGs indicators showed that 35.29% of the geographical
 415 areas were graded below the mean (see [Error! Reference source not found.](#)). There is no
 416 either where the majority of SDGs were rated over the average either (see [Figure 5](#)), not even

417 in rich zones such as North America, Europe or Oceania. Therefore, these figures are very far
418 from the goals to be achieved by 2030.

419

420 **4. Conclusions**

421

422 This article appraised the suitability of using the 2017 SDG Index to monitor progress of
423 the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development through the assessment of SDGs. The main
424 conclusions drawn from this article are as follows:

425 • Existing global aggregate indices do not consider major factors of all sustainability
426 pillars, being biased towards some of them. Furthermore, regional sustainable
427 development plans focus on their specific geographic areas without envisaging numerous
428 indicators included in the SDGs. Thus, none of them can be deemed as global sustainable
429 development composite indices nor as an accurate measure to appraise the fulfilment of
430 the SDGs.

431 • Severe limitations in collecting data about SDGs indicators hinder their proper
432 assessment. This circumstance makes about 60% of the measures set to monitor progress
433 towards sustainable development useless.

434 • The selection of unmeasurable metrics greatly undermines the potential success of the
435 2030 Agenda. The adoption of further statistical practices should be highly encouraged to
436 provide missing information and enable the evaluation of all nations with less than one
437 million inhabitants.

438 • The consideration of inadequate spillover indicators to evaluate the effects caused by
439 some nations on other countries can seriously distort the marks of some richer regions
440 across the SDGs, due to the intricate links among the actions undertaken and their
441 repercussions.

442 • The relevance of social and economic issues in the SDGs prevails over other
443 sustainability aspects like the environment, which predominated in past global initiatives.

444 • Adjustments on the proportion of 2017 SDG Index indicators in each sustainability
445 dimension can alter the assessment of sustainable development as specified in the 2030
446 Agenda.

447 • Paradoxically, the most developed economies (Europe, North America and Oceania)
448 revealed low average scores in responsible consumption and production in comparison
449 with poorer countries. North America also held the lowest mark in partnership for the
450 goals.

451 In summary, the selection of indicators with extensive available data is a key factor for
452 constructing useful composite indices as integrated frameworks to appraise the achievement
453 of the SDGs at a country scale. Changes in the distribution of the SDG Index indicators in
454 relation to that of the SDGs framework and the inclusion of spillovers can severely disrupt
455 accurate valuations. Moreover, differentiating national factors in geographical areas should
456 stress the importance of some goals in detriment of others almost already achieved.
457 Consequently, the findings of this research suggest the implementation of customized SDG
458 Indices to enhance the appraisal of specific regions.

459

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